

IMPROVEMENT OF THE METHOD OF MANUFACTURING SEMI-FINISHED PRODUCTS OF A HIGH DEGREE OF READINESS FROM JERUSALEM ARTICHOKE TUBERS

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Abstract

A method has been improved for the production of semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness from Jerusalem artichoke tubers, characterized by a significant natural content of functional and physiological ingredients and health-improving properties to ensure a wide range of uses in processing complexes. The method is distinguished by blanching with hot steam at a pressure in the working chamber of 0.1 MPa for 8...10 min, followed by rubbing to an average particle size of 30...50 µm with a content of 10...11+2 % SR. Subsequent heating of the puree-like mass to 40...45 °C and concentration in a rotary-film evaporator to a content of 20...30+2 % DM at a temperature of 55...60 °C for 55...95 s. The technology for producing concentrated paste from Jerusalem artichoke tubers allows preserving the biological potential of raw materials during the concentration process due to gentle low-temperature processing.

The content of functionally physiological ingredients of the puree mass was determined: active acidity – 4.2 pH, dietary fiber – 3.3 g/100 g puree, pectin – 1.25 %, inulin – 10.05 g/100 g puree, and are also important.

According to an improved method for the production of a pasty semi-finished product from Jerusalem artichoke tuber, an apparatus-technological scheme is proposed. The selected equipment line is distinguished by resource efficiency and small overall dimensions and can be located in the places where raw materials are collected. The produced paste-like semi-finished product of a high degree of readiness from Jerusalem artichoke contains (in gr): mono- and disaccharides – 3.6; inulin – 20.3; starch – 10.7; dietary fiber – 14.4 and organic acid – 0.11 and has attractive organoleptic properties. A pasty semi-finished product of a high degree of readiness has been made, which can be recommended as a vitamin supplement (filler) in the production of functional products in various areas of the food and processing industry.

Keywords: Jerusalem artichoke, pasty semi-finished product, functional and physiological ingredients, concentration.

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1. Introduction

Ensuring rational nutrition in many countries of the world is an integral part of modern processing complexes aimed at the production of semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness

to expand the range of products with a high content of functionally physiological ingredients [1, 2]. One of the sources of rational nutrition is the use of natural raw materials with a significant content of useful micro- and macroelements, original organoleptic properties, as well as dyes [3, 4]. However, the processing of vegetable raw materials requires high-quality resource-efficient implementation at all instrumental and technological stages, forming the prerequisites for the maximum preservation of natural properties.

Modern research on improving the method of production of semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness, intended to expand the health-improving assortment of food products, is relevant [5]. The creation of high-quality vegetable semi-finished products is based on the use of resource-efficient hardware-technological complexes in conditions of low-temperature heat and mass transfer operations. Thus, forming before the processing-industrial complexes the need for intensification of the production link [6].

An important stage in the production of pasty semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness is the blanching of pre-prepared vegetable raw materials, followed by obtaining a puree-like mass on double mashing machines and subsequent concentration of the required dry matter content [7]. The classical technology of boiling natural purees is implemented in vacuum evaporators with a duration of the technological process from 80 to 400 minutes, depending on the degree of boiling, which largely affects the preservation of the initial natural properties [8].

The aim of the work is to improve the method for the production of semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness in the conditions of the implementation of resource-efficient low-temperature regimes. This, in turn, will make it possible to produce health-improving semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness with a wide range of uses in various food products: confectionery, pasta, etc. Providing the resulting products with original organoleptic properties and increasing the content of therapeutic and prophylactic properties, forming a competitive production and demand for the consumption of these products [9].

For example, in terms of nutritional value and content of micro- and macroelements, Jerusalem artichoke surpasses many vegetables several times, the energy value of 100 g of raw Jerusalem artichoke tuber is 57.3 kcal. Jerusalem artichoke tubers are mixed with a significant content of protein, mineral salt, inulin (from 16 to 18 %), fructose, etc. Jerusalem artichoke contains fiber, vitamins: B1, B2, B3, B6, B9, C, PP, carotenoids, amino acids (including 8 essential amino acids: arginine, histidine, valine, leucine, isoleucine, lysine, tryptophan, methionine) and pectins, etc. In terms of iron content, Jerusalem artichoke is superior to more practical vegetables: carrots, tubers, turnips, beets and others. The amino acid arginine plays an important role in the production of growth hormones, increases potency and strengthens the immune system. The amino acid lysine is involved in the process of hematopoiesis, the natural production of collagen, the natural synthesis of enzymes, hormones and antibodies, and also contributes to the effective absorption of calcium necessary for bones and joints [10]. The processing of Jerusalem artichoke into semi-finished products with a high natural content of functionally physiological ingredients and their subsequent use in various food products will help expand the range of health products [11, 12].

In order to achieve the goals set to improve the method for the production of semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness, it is proposed to use Jerusalem artichoke tubers during their processing using gentle low-temperature heat and mass transfer processing to maximize the biological potential. This will ensure the formation of a competitive instrumental and technological component of the processing of natural raw materials with the simultaneous expansion of health-improving products with a wide range of uses, which is important in the conditions of the ecological situation in many countries in the conditions of the formation of immunity strength [13, 14].

2. Materials and methods of research

For research, Jerusalem artichoke tubers of variety “Nakhodka” (Fig. 1), collected in the Kharkiv region in 2022, were selected.

The analysis of Jerusalem artichoke tubers and the resulting semi-finished products was carried out according to traditional methods, namely: physicochemical, organoleptic and microbiological. The mass fraction of solids was determined according to GOST 28561-90, the con-

tent of vitamins B1 and B2 in Jerusalem artichoke tubers and puree was determined according to GOST 25999-83. Determination of the content of dietary fiber in Jerusalem artichoke tubers was determined according to GOST R 54014-2010. Titrated and active acidity was determined by titrimetric and potentiometric methods according to GOST 25555.0-82.

For the production of semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness from Jerusalem artichoke tubers, a schematic diagram was formed (Fig. 2) indicating the main technological operations and regime parameters.

Fig. 1. Appearance of the experimental tuber of Jerusalem artichoke variety “Nakhodka”

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the production of semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness from Jerusalem artichoke tubers

The first stage in the processing of Jerusalem artichoke tubers is sorting on belt conveyors in order to select low-quality root crops and subsequent calibration, after which the washing stage is carried out by rinsing on fan washing machines.

To soften the structure of tubers before wiping, blanching with hot steam was carried out in functional apparatuses at a pressure in the working chamber of 0.1 MPa for 8–10 min, followed by peeling. After the tuber, they go for coarse grinding in sizes of 0.1...2.5 mm, followed by the addition of citric acid (approximately 0.05 % of the total mass of the crushed puree). Fine grinding of preliminary crushed Jerusalem artichoke mass is carried out on universal rubbing machines with an average particle size in the range of 30...50 microns, while the dry matter content (DM) is about 10...11+2 %.

The mashed puree mass of Jerusalem artichoke first enters the storage tank with heating –40 ... 45 °C and is pumped by a gear pump into a rotary-film evaporator [15] with subsequent concentration to a content of 20...30+2 %. The concentration process is carried out at a temperature of 55...60 °C and lasts for 55...95 seconds.

A pasty semi-finished product of a high degree of readiness from Jerusalem artichoke tubers, after concentrating in a rotary-film apparatus, enters the final technological stage of production – packaging with subsequent sale.

The physicochemical and organoleptic properties of puree from Jerusalem artichoke tubers were also determined (**Table 1**).

Table 1

Physicochemical and organoleptic properties of puree from Jerusalem artichoke tubers

Indicator	Properties/parameters
Physico-chemical characteristics	
Mass fraction of solids, %:	15.00
Active acidity, pH	4.2
Mass fraction of reducing substances, %	3.0
pectin substances	1.25
Dietary fiber, g/100 g puree	3.30
Inulin, g/100 g puree	10.05
Amino acids, %:	
Arginine	0.10
Valine	0.07
Lysine	0.03
Tyrosine	0.02
Isoleucine	0.04
Methionine	0.06
Serene	0.05
Proline	0.04
Threonine	0.05
Aspartic acid	0.3
Organoleptic indicators:	
Consistency	homogeneous mass without foreign impurities
Smell	characteristic of Jerusalem artichoke
Color	faint green tint
Taste	sweet characteristic taste of Jerusalem artichoke

The analysis of the data obtained confirms the significant content of functionally physiological ingredients for the subsequent production of semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness by the proposed method. In particular: active acidity is 4.2. pH, dietary fiber – 3.3 g/100 g puree, pectin – 1.25 %, inulin – 10.05 g/100 g puree, there are also important amino acids and attractive organoleptic properties (**Table 1**).

3. Research results and their discussion

Taking into account the proposed principle scheme for the production of semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness from Jerusalem artichoke tubers, an apparatus-technological scheme is proposed, shown in **Fig. 3**.

The proposed hardware-technological scheme for the production of highly prepared concentrated semi-finished products from Jerusalem artichoke tubers is characterized by resource-efficient processing with maximum preservation of natural properties and physical and chemical ingredients.

The use of a rotary film evaporator makes it possible to implement the concentration process to a content of 45...75 % DM, and for example, the boiling of fruit, berry and vegetable blends is carried out up to 25...35 % DM [16]. Significantly expanding the range of use of the production of concentrated semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness from Jerusalem artichoke tubers obtained by the proposed method in processing and production complexes.

Table 2 shows the chemical composition of the concentrated paste from Jerusalem artichoke tubers with organoleptic characteristics.

Table 2

Chemical composition of concentrated paste from Jerusalem artichoke tubers

Name of nutrients (g)	Contents of 100 g concentrated paste
Water	35.2
Squirrels	2.1
Fats	0.11
Mono- and disaccharides	3.6
Inulin	20.3
Starch	10.7
Alimentary fiber	14.4
Organic acids	0.11
Vitamins (mg)	
A (retinol)	0.18
B1 (thiamine)	0.05
B2 (riboflavin)	0.04
B6 (pyridoxine)	0.3
B9 (folic acid)	17.2
Vitamin C	6.53
Organoleptic indicators:	
Consistency	homogeneous mass
Smell	characteristic of Jerusalem artichoke
Color	faint yellow tint
Taste	sweet characteristic taste of Jerusalem artichoke

The technology for obtaining a concentrated paste from Jerusalem artichoke tubers makes it possible to preserve the functional and physiological composition in the process of concentration due to low-temperature gentle treatment to a content of mass fraction of solids of 50...70 %. Despite the fact that traditional technologies for boiling vegetable raw materials provide concentration of up to 25–35 % DM [17].

The concentrated semi-finished product of a high degree of readiness, in accordance with the obtained physico-chemical content, has in its composition (in gr.): Mono- and disaccharides – 3.6; inulin – 20.3; starch – 10.7; dietary fiber – 14.4 and organic acid – 0.11. In addition, a significant content of various vitamins and attractive organoleptic properties. The limitation of the above studies lies in the need to comply with the hardware and technological recommendations in the production of semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness from Jerusalem artichoke tubers, since neglecting them will lead to changes in the resulting quality of the products as a whole.

Fig. 3. Hardware-technological scheme for the production of semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness from Jerusalem artichoke tubers: 1 – inspection conveyor; 2 – calibration conveyor; 3 – fan washer; 4 – functional apparatus for blanching; 5 – universal double wiping machine; 6 – gear pump; 7 – heater; 8 – rotary film evaporator; 9 – packing machine

4. Conclusions

The method for the production of semi-finished products of a high degree of readiness from Jerusalem artichoke tubers, characterized by a significant natural content of functional and physiological ingredients and health-improving properties, has been improved, providing a wide range of uses in processing complexes. For practical-experimental testing of the improved method, a tuber of the Jerusalem artichoke variety “Nakhodka” harvested in 2022 is proposed. The method is distinguished by blanching with hot steam at a pressure in the working chamber of 0.1 MPa for 8...10 min, followed by rubbing to an average particle size of 30...50 μm with a content of 10...11+2 % DM. Subsequent heating of the puree-like mass to 40...45 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and concentration in a rotary-film evaporator to a content of 20...30+2 % DM at a temperature of 55...60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 55...95 sec. The content of functionally physiological ingredients of the puree mass was determined: active acidity – 4.2 pH, dietary fiber – 3.3 g/100 g puree, pectin – 1.25 %, inulin – 10.05 g/100 g puree, and are also important.

Taking into account the useful properties of Jerusalem artichoke tubers, an apparatus-technological scheme for the production of highly prepared concentrated semi-finished products from Jerusalem artichoke tubers is proposed. The use of a rotary-film evaporator makes it possible to implement the concentration process up to a content of 45...75 % DM. A pasty semi-finished product of a high degree of readiness from Jerusalem artichoke contains (in grams): mono- and disaccharides – 3.6; inulin – 20.3; starch – 10.7; dietary fiber – 14.4 and organic acid – 0.11 and has attractive organoleptic properties. Expanding the directions of use of the obtained health-improving paste-like semi-finished product of a high degree of readiness as a vitamin supplement (filler) in the production of functional products in various areas of the food and processing industry.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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